

SHTOLS TEOREMASI VA UNING TATBIQLARI

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Annotatsiya: Shtols teoremasi matematik analizdagi muhim teorema hisoblanadi. Quyida teorema isboti va xalqaro olimpiadalarda tadbirlarini ko'rib chiqamiz.

Kalit sozlar: limit, Shtols teoremasi, monoton ketma-ketliklar.

Teorema(Shtols). Bizga ikkita $(a_n)_{n \geq 1}$ va $(b_n)_{n \geq 1}$ ketma-ketliklar berilgan bo'lsin:

1) $(b_n)_{n \geq 1}$ ketma-ketlik qat'iy o'suvchi va

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} b_n = \infty$$

bo'lsin;

2) Quyidagi limit mavjud bo'lsin:

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{a_{n+1} - a_n}{b_{n+1} - b_n} = l$$

U holda quyidagi ketma-ketlik yaqinlashuvchi va

$$\left\{ \frac{a_n}{b_n} \right\}$$

uning limiti l ga teng, ya'ni

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{a_n}{b_n} = l$$

Isbot. Teorema shartida $(b_n)_{n \geq 1}$ ketma-ketlik qat'iy o'suvchi va limiti ∞ ga teng.

Demak, ketma-ketligimiz biror joydan ($n = n_0$ chi hadidan boshlab) musbat qiymat qabul qilib boshlaydi va

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{a_{n+1} - a_n}{b_{n+1} - b_n} = l$$

limiti mavjud.

$\forall \varepsilon > 0$ berilganda ham $\exists m \in \mathbb{N}$ mavjudki $\forall n \geq m$ natural sonlar uchun

$$\left| \frac{a_{n+1} - a_n}{b_{n+1} - b_n} - l \right| < \varepsilon$$

bo‘ladi. Bundan quyidagini yozib olamiz

$$(l - \varepsilon)(b_{n+1} - b_n) < a_{n+1} - a_n < (l + \varepsilon)(b_{n+1} - b_n)$$

endi n ni k bilan, $k+1$ bilan $k+2$ bilan va hokazo $n-1$ bilan almashtirib yozamiz:

$$(l - \varepsilon)(b_{k+1} - b_k) < a_{k+1} - a_k < (l + \varepsilon)(b_{k+1} - b_k)$$

$$(l - \varepsilon)(b_{k+2} - b_{k+1}) < a_{k+2} - a_{k+1} < (l + \varepsilon)(b_{k+2} - b_{k+1})$$

$$(l - \varepsilon)(b_{k+3} - b_{k+2}) < a_{k+3} - a_{k+2} < (l + \varepsilon)(b_{k+3} - b_{k+2})$$

.....

$$(l - \varepsilon)(b_n - b_{n-1}) < a_n - a_{n-1} < (l + \varepsilon)(b_n - b_{n-1})$$

Bu ifodalarni qo‘shib yuborsak

$$(l - \varepsilon)(b_n - b_k) < a_n - a_k < (l + \varepsilon)(b_n - b_k)$$

bu ifodani b_n ga bo‘lamiz:

$$(l - \varepsilon) \left(1 - \frac{b_k}{b_n} \right) < \frac{a_n - a_k}{b_n - b_k} < (l + \varepsilon) \left(1 - \frac{b_k}{b_n} \right)$$

$$l - \varepsilon + \frac{a_k + (\varepsilon - l)b_k}{b_n} < \frac{a_n}{b_n} < l + \varepsilon + \frac{a_k - (\varepsilon + l)b_k}{b_n}$$

bilamizki

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{a_k + (\varepsilon - l)b_k}{b_n} = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{a_k - (\varepsilon + l)b_k}{b_n} = 0$$

yuqoridagi $\forall \varepsilon > 0$ kora $\exists k \in \mathbb{N}$ mavjudki $\forall n \geq k$ natural sonlar uchun quyidagilar o‘rinli:

$$-\varepsilon < \frac{a_k + (\varepsilon - l)b_k}{b_n} < \varepsilon$$

$$-\varepsilon < \frac{a_k - (\varepsilon + l)b_k}{b_n} < \varepsilon.$$

Endi $p = \max\{m, p\}$ deb olsak, $\forall n \geq p$ natural sonlar uchun yuqoridagi ikkita tengsizligimiz bir vaqtda bajariladi. Quyidagiga ega bo‘lamiz

$$l - 2\varepsilon < l - \varepsilon + \frac{a_k + (\varepsilon - l)b_k}{b_n} < \frac{a_n}{b_n} < l + \varepsilon + \frac{a_k - (\varepsilon + l)b_k}{b_n} < l + 2\varepsilon$$

$$l - 2\varepsilon < \frac{a_n}{b_n} < l + 2\varepsilon$$

$$\left| \frac{a_n}{b_n} - l \right| < 2\varepsilon$$

ε sonining ixtiyoriyligidan 2ε ixtiyoriy son bo'ladi. Ketma-ketlik limit tarifidan

$$\left\{ \frac{a_n}{b_n} \right\}$$

Ketma-ketlik yaqinlashuvchi va limiti l ga teng.

Teorema to'liq isbotlandi.

Endi teoremani olimpiada misoliga tatbiq etamiz

Misol. Quyidagi ketma-ketlikning $n \rightarrow \infty$ limitni hisoblang:

$$z_n = (1 + 11^n)^{\frac{1}{n+2}}$$

Yechilishi: $z_n = (1 + 11^n)^{\frac{1}{n+2}}$ bu ketma-ketlikni Shtols teoremasini qanoatlantirishi uchun quyidagicha shakl almashtirish bajaramiz:

$$z_n = (1 + 11^n)^{\frac{1}{n+2}} = e^{\frac{1}{n+2} \ln(1 + 11^n)}$$

Endi z_n ketma-ketlikni x_n va y_n ketma-ketliklar orqali ifodalaymiz:

$x_n = \ln(1 + 11^n)$, $y_n = n + 2$. Bunda ketma-ketlik quyidagi ko'rinishni oladi:

$$z_n = e^{\frac{x_n}{y_n}}$$

Bilamizki,

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} z_n = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} e^{\frac{x_n}{y_n}} = e^{\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{x_n}{y_n}}$$

munosabat o'rinli. Endi $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{x_n}{y_n}$ qiymatini topish bilan shug'ullanamiz. Bu yerda

$x_n = \ln(1 + 11^n)$, $y_n = n + 2$ hamda y_n qat'iy o'suvchi: $y_{n+1} > y_n$. Shtols teoremasining shartlarini qanoatlantirdi. Endi

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{x_{n+1} - x_n}{y_{n+1} - y_n}$$

limitni hisoblaymiz:

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\ln(1+11^{n+1}) - \ln(1+11^n)}{(n+3) - (n+2)} = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \ln \left(\frac{1+11^{n+1}}{1+11^n} \right) = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \ln \left(\frac{\frac{1}{11^n} + 11}{\frac{1}{11^n} + 1} \right) = \ln 11$$

Shtols teoremasiga ko‘ra

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{x_n}{y_n} = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{x_{n+1} - x_n}{y_{n+1} - y_n}$$

munosabat o‘rinli. Bundan $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{x_n}{y_n} = \ln 11$ ekanligi kelib chiqadi. Endi bu qiymatni

o‘rniga qo‘yib berilgan ketma-ketlikning $n \rightarrow \infty$ dagi limitini hisoblaymiz:

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} z_n = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} e^{\frac{x_n}{y_n}} = e^{\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{x_n}{y_n}} = e^{\ln 11} = 11$$

Demak,

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} (1+11^n)^{\frac{1}{n+2}} = 11.$$

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar:

1. **Azlarov T., Mansurov H** Matematik analiz: Unversitet va ped. Institut talabalari uchun darslik: 2 qismli. 1-q. –qayta ishlangan va toldirilgan 2-nashri. –T.: Oqituvchi, 1994.-416 b
2. Brainkart.com.

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